

Worldwide Systems and Applications

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ABSTRACT

Worldwide photovoltaics (PV) sales are expected to increase at an annual rate of over 20% in 1991 despite a lull in growth during 1990. Faster growth can be attributed to increase in demand by traditional remote power market customers and newer customers such as electric utilities, as well as increased sensitivity to environmental degradation; the availability of improved products and broader product lines; better product delivery networks; and improved economics. The Department of Energy, in partnership with the U.S. PV industry, major customer groups, and regulatory bodies has embarked on an aggressive program of market conditioning and project development that supplements its traditional R&D role. This program, SOLAR 2000, has set a goal of achieving a worldwide installation of 1,500 MW of U.S. PV systems by the year 2000.

INTRODUCTION

The cost of electricity from photovoltaics (PV) has declined from about 90¢/kWh in 1980 to 30¢/kWh today. During this period, the strong U.S. industry and government partnership has continued with a total U.S. industrial investment of \$2 billion. The federal government investment during the 1980s was \$569 million (1).

The demand for PV continues to grow rapidly as PV prices decline, product quality improves, and environmental concerns enhance the value of PV. Manufacturers are responding by increasing production and supplying a greater variety of systems. While the traditional customer base continues to expand, newer customers are entering the market for larger systems and for systems to serve niche markets with very specific requirements. The potential for PV has hardly been tapped, but accelerating the adoption of PV requires a multifaceted approach that continues technological advances while concurrently conditioning the market and encouraging project development.

PV MARKET GROWTH

Worldwide PV module shipments grew 15% between 1985 and 1990 (Table I). Between 1989 and 1990, module shipments in Europe increased the fastest at 25% compared to an 18%

increase in Japan. The growth in U.S. shipments was a low 6%, partly attributable to the restructuring of Chronar, and the renovation of the Sovonics plant (2). Increased demand for PV by Europe due to major projects in Germany, Italy and Switzerland, helped Japanese and American exports. However, these exports may be a relatively short term phenomenon as European manufacturers are adding new capacity.

Table I - Worldwide Photovoltaic Sales (2),(3)

	'85	'86	'87	'88	'89	'90	'91
USA	7.7	7.1	8.7	11.3	14.1	14.6	
Japan	10.3	12.6	13.2	12.8	14.2	16.8	
Europe	3.4	4.0	4.5	6.7	7.9	10.2	
Other	1.4	2.3	2.8	3.0	4.4	4.7	
TOTAL	22.8	26.0	29.2	33.8	40.3	46.5	58 -62

MARKET SEGMENTATION

Figure 1 shows the market segmentation of U.S. PV systems for 1985 and 1990. The export market has increased in importance with the market share rising to 43% from 36% in 1985, reflecting in part, the rising European demand. Remote applications in the industrial and commercial sectors have gained a significantly greater market share, and this trend is likely to continue. The remote homes market share has remained flat although in MW terms, sales have nearly doubled. U.S. firms have made the greatest gain in consumer products market which has historically been dominated by Japanese companies. The consumer products market constitutes applications needing very small amounts of power (less than 10W).

CURRENT STATUS OF PV SYSTEMS AND MARKETS

Photovoltaics and PV hybrids are now being used the world over for remote power applications where PV's advantages of high reliability, minimal maintenance, and no fuel requirements have been particularly valuable (Table II). Around 97% of U.S. PV sales in 1990 were for off-grid applications (2).

Table II - PV Remote Power Applications

Representative PV Remote Power Applications	
Battery charging	Remote residences
Cathodic protection	River gauging
Telecommunications	SCADA stations
Emergency call boxes	Sectionalizing
Electric fencing	switches
Gas flow metering	Sign boards
Lighting	Signalling, monitoring
Meteorological stations	Transmitters
Microwave repeaters	Valve actuators
Navigational aids	Water quality
Refrigeration	monitoring
Remote gates	Water pumping,
Remote meter readers	purification

Photovoltaics is the most pervasive renewable energy technology in use today. It is being used as far south as Antarctica and as far north as Norway and Alaska. It is used in deserts, in rain forests, and in every developed or developing country. Remote power applications using stand-alone PV systems dominate these uses.

Figure 1 U.S. PV Market Segmentation in 1985 and 1990

Unlike PV module costs, battery costs have not been declining, and will constitute an increasingly larger share of a PV system's costs. Therefore, PV/diesel/wind hybrids will gain in importance as they are effective in reducing the amount of battery storage required without compromising reliability. The advent of improved "intelligent" controllers have broadened the applicability of PV hybrids. In the past, hybrids were predominantly used for applications such as telecommunications where very high reliability was necessary. They are now beginning to be used for rural electrification to supply utility grade power to villages. A large PV hybrid

system on Coconut Island in northern Australia, has now been supplying 250 kWh/day for three years with an overall availability of 99.8% (4). Integrated Power Corporation installed a PV/diesel/wind hybrid system in the Santa Maria Magdalena village in Mexico that delivers 50 kWh/day (5). Recently, Indonesia ordered two PV/diesel/wind hybrids and one PV/diesel hybrid to serve three island communities (6). Each delivers 100 kWh/day of utility grade power.

Utilities are finding an increasing number of applications for PV where it is more cost-effective than extending the grid or using step down transformers. About 20 utilities in the U.S. are using PV for small power applications (7). PG&E alone has over 700 systems in use. Many of the remote power applications listed in Table II are now being adopted by utilities.

Utilities are now considering offering PV in lieu of grid extension to customers who are some distance from the grid. Analyses by the Department of Energy have shown that for electricity use of around 1500 kWh a month (the equivalent of 2 U.S. residences), PV is currently cost-competitive with grid extension for line lengths exceeding 5 miles (8). PG&E finds that for residences requiring only a 2 kW PV system, the breakeven distance is one third mile (9). There appears to be a considerable demand for such applications. For example, PG&E is turning away more than 200 customers a year who are too far from the grid line due to the very high cost of grid extension (10). KC Electric Association in rural Colorado now offers PV systems to customers who have remote water pumping needs. They find that a PV pumping system is less costly to install and maintain than a power line to the pumping site.

Utilities are also beginning to consider using PV for line-connected demand side management applications. Demand side management is valuable for utilities because it can delay or indefinitely defer building new peak generation capacity. A 15.4 kW roof-mounted PV array installed by Niagara Mohawk Power Corporation in Albany NY is the test bed to determine if PV can be effective in shaving the peak loads which correlate well with sunshine intensity (11). The initial results look promising, but further investigations are needed to optimally configure the system. A similar investigation at the Virginia Tech Solar Experiment Station is also producing encouraging results (12). In this study the capability of a PV array to reduce a building's daily peak demand from 830 kW to less than 650 kW was demonstrated. Based on Virginia Power rates for large general service customers, the total savings for the building owner who installs a PV peak shaver, in terms of reduced demand and distribution charges, and energy costs is \$2,100/month (13). This estimate assumes that the demand charge saving occurs every month, and the energy savings is equivalent to electricity produced by a 180 kW (AC) PV system at an average of 5 peak hours of sunlight daily.

Investigations by Shugar have shown that PV can be an economic alternative to upgrading a substation which has a

afternoon peaking load (14). The principal value of PV is in its capacity to delay upgrading the transformer, in reducing T&D and transformer losses, increasing reliability, providing kVAR support, and in saving energy and generating capacity. PV would be economic by 1992 for this application if federal and state tax credits were available. By 1995, PV could be economic without tax credits.

Since the early 1980s utilities have also been interested in PV as a bulk power supplier of the future. A number of demonstration projects have continued since that time. Carissa Plains PV system was the world's largest PV central generating station with a 1985 installed capacity of 8 MW AC (15). The system performed exceptionally well with availability of 97% during 1985 to 1988.

The City of Austin is testing two large PV power plants. One is a 250 kW (AC) flat plate array installed in 1986, and the other is a 248 kW (AC) concentrating field. In 1990, the flat plate system had an availability of 99.6% for the whole year, while the concentrating array availability was 89.6% from July through December. Both systems demonstrated the capability of PV to meet peak demands. During the peak summer hours of 5 to 6pm, the concentrating array delivered 49% of its capacity, and the flat plate array delivered 63% of its rated capacity (16).

Photovoltaics for Utility Scale Applications (PVUSA) is the first nationwide cooperative demonstration project in the U.S.A. The goals of the project are to demonstrate PV technologies in a utility setting and to establish a dialogue between the PV industry and utilities. During 1990, eight 20 kW Emerging Module Technology (EMT) systems, one 400 kW and two 200 kW utility scalable systems were tested (17).

Similar grid-connected applications are being tested in Italy, Switzerland and Germany. The Italian National Energy Plan expected that 25 MW of PV would be installed in Italy by 1995 (18). The Swiss have installed 100 kW of grid-connected PV on existing sound barriers along a motorway. The Swiss project demonstrates the capability of PV to be fully integrated into structures thus eliminating the need for dedicating valuable land area for power generation. A similar project in Germany is installing PV on roofs. The project expects to install 2,400 roof-mounted, 1-5 kW PV systems on roofs by 1995 (19).

OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE 1990s

Tremendous opportunities exist for PV to assist in meeting the energy needs of the 1990s and beyond. Nearly 600 GW of new generating capacity may be required worldwide between 1990 and 2000 (20) (Table III). In the U.S., the National Energy Strategy estimates a need for over 100 GW of new generating capacity in the 1990s and nearly 90 GW in the first decade of the 2000s. Overall, for over two thirds of the utilities in the U.S., generating requirements are expected to

grow at or less than 100 MW per year, with more than 88% of the utilities having requirements of less than 250 MW per year. Moreover, capacity additions can be deferred by implementing DSM programs where PV could play a significant role.

In the international marketplace, the next ten years anticipate a need for nearly 500 GW of new generating capacity. Developing countries alone will require about 350 GW of capacity, with India and China accounting for over 50 percent of this increase.

Despite these large capacity increases, a large proportion of rural communities in developing countries will continue to lack access to electric power due to the cost and difficulty of extending transmission and distribution systems to dispersed communities. The power requirements of most nonelectrified rural communities in developing countries are modest, with primary batteries, kerosene (for lighting), and gasoline and diesel generators providing most of the energy. The aggregate remote electric power requirements are huge --there is an estimated 2 billion people who do not have access to electricity, and there are 10 million small (less than 200 kW) diesel generators operating in the sun belt around the world with 2 million new generators sold annually. The modularity, ease of maintenance, and independence from fossil fuel supplies makes PV systems ideally suited for remote off-grid applications.

Table III 1990 to 2000 Worldwide Electric Power Capacity Requirements

REGION	CAPACITY (GW)
U.S.A.	
Region I - New England	3.5
Region II - New York/New Jersey	6.8
Region III - Mid-Atlantic	10.9
Region IV - South Atlantic	22.9
Region V - Midwest	15.5
Region VI - Southwest	14.6
Region VII - Central	11.6
Region VIII - North Central	4.3
Region IX - West	12.2
Region X - Northwest	3.6
OECD - Europe	48
Eastern Europe	22
Asia	244
Japan	20
Middle East & North Africa	47
Latin America & Caribbean	66
OECD - Other	16

Complementing this worldwide demand for new generating capacity are emerging conditions in the U.S. that encourage innovative technology solutions. These evolving market conditions are demonstrated by a greater emphasis on integrated resource planning (IRP); increased activity by non-utility wholesale power generators who are less constrained than investor owned utilities (IOUs) in their choice of generating technology, the legal and administrative requirements, and risk taking; a National Energy Strategy in 1991 that calls for enhanced R&D funding for renewable technologies; rising environmental concerns; recognition by federal and state regulators of the inadequacy of existing regulations to provide utility incentives for investment and cost-sharing innovations; and an improving business and political climate for commercially viable PV projects as demonstrated by Congressional authorization, in March 1991, for \$100 million for the deployment of 10 PV demonstration projects (each at least 10 MW in size) (21).

ATTAINING THE POTENTIAL OF PV: THE SOLAR 2000 STRATEGY

The opportunities for greater PV use are abundant, but several barriers currently limit its market growth. To mitigate technological and market barriers the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) has embarked upon an aggressive and ambitious program known as SOLAR 2000. The program is a collaborative effort between the industry, the investors, the regulators, policymakers, utilities, and other customers. The role of DOE in Solar 2000 is to bring these stakeholders together to rapidly achieve a fully articulated market for PV. Solar 2000 expects to:

- Increase access to research and development funds to further improve the efficiencies, and scale-up manufacturing and production.
- Condition the marketplace, particularly in the regulatory and policy areas, to encourage more equitable consideration of solar electric technologies.
- Enhance the acceptance of solar electric technologies by supporting project development and implementation to provide the performance, availability, operation and maintenance, and cost information at user sites.
- Increase education, promotion, and technology transfer activities.

The Solar 2000 program will be DOE's vehicle in extending PV from primarily remote off-grid uses to the much larger market for distributed and bulk power applications. The Solar 2000 strategy involves coordinated action on three fronts -- technology development and validation, market conditioning, and project development -- which combine to address existing barriers in the domestic and foreign power supply marketplace.

Technology Development and Validation

DOE will pursue its aggressive PV R&D program, and enhance its resource assessment program. In anticipation that PV will be increasingly used in grid-connected and bulk power systems, DOE will extend its systems development efforts beyond remote off-grid applications to large-scale power generation systems. The Technology Development and Validation effort focuses on three major elements:

- **Research and Development** which addresses scientific and engineering questions pertaining to the conversion efficiencies of PV materials, cells and devices.
- **Manufacturing and Technology Development** which seeks to improve PV manufacturing processes to reduce the cost of modules.
- **Systems Development** which assesses the performance and reliability of today's PV systems and develop ways to improve those systems for both near- and long-term market applications. A major emphasis of this element is on collaborative projects with industry and utilities at utility sites which promise to secure improved technologies, enhance end-user experience, and increase industry capabilities to service utility needs. The Photovoltaics for Utility Scale Applications (PVUSA) is a key component of this collaborative R&D effort between government, the PV industry, and utilities.

Market Conditioning

Improvements in PV technology and systems alone do not ensure success in the marketplace. The marketplace requires access to accurate and complete information on the available technologies. Potential PV users must be given the tools with which to analyze the costs, benefits and risks of PV systems which often do not fit into traditional decision-making models. Regulators and policymakers must also level the playing field across energy technologies to ensure that PV is not at a permanent disadvantage owing to its higher initial capital requirements. A **Communications and Technology Transfer Program** and a **Decision Analysis and Standards Program** will assist in increasing the market acceptance of PV.

Project Development

Beyond the technical and market barriers to large-scale PV development lies the large obstacle of risk which often prevents investment in PV development. New technologies and applications that have not been commercially demonstrated and adopted on a wide-scale are perceived by regulators, investors, utilities and other end-users as risky ventures. This perception has, in part, been created by the experience of the late 1970's and early 1980's when another capital-intensive technology -- nuclear -- experienced large cost overruns, higher fuel costs, and public opposition.

Although worldwide demand for clean energy is quickly growing, PV must overcome a number of perceived risks, such as:

- **Technology risk** -- the possibility that the technology will not perform as specified;
- **Construction risk** -- the possibility of cost overruns/inability to meet schedule;
- **Operating risk** -- the possibility of breakdown, unavailability of power when needed;
- **Regulatory and tax risk** -- the possibility, in the utility market, of having the investment disallowed during prudency reviews, tax credits or accelerated depreciation expire, or other regulatory uncertainty;
- **Financial limitations** -- the high cost of financing due to perceptions of the above risks.

Project Development aims to reduce perceived technology risks; increase investor, end-user and manufacturer experience with PV systems; and help build a critical mass of applications needed for "market take-off." The program also assists the effort to deploy U.S. PV systems overseas to prevent the U.S. from being shut out of foreign markets.

Under Project Development, DOE will participate as a player to reduce risks and thereby stimulate project development by end-users. Mitigating these risks involves:

- Supporting cooperative efforts which reduce the threshold of risk for investors new to PV technologies in various end-use sectors;
- Procuring solar electric technologies for government applications to help establish the track record for PV technology;
- Absorbing some of the cost of project development where the rewards in the short-term are insufficient to stimulate private investment in demonstration projects.

DOE is currently involved in, or considering participating in a number of PV development projects which it hopes will provide the performance data necessary to build the trust of future investors in distributed and bulk power PV systems.

Investor Owned Utility (IOU) PV Cooperative Venture. Together with the Solar Energy Industries Association (SEIA), DOE is part of a collaborative effort to establish a group of IOUs committed to procure increasing amounts of PV power each year through the year 2000. Each utility will procure systems separately, and the group as a whole will meet to establish targets. High value utility-related applications will comprise the initial market segment. This effort will achieve the deployment of 100 MW of PV by 2000.

American Public Power Association (APPA) PV Cooperative Venture. This venture focuses on gaining the participation of public utilities in the same manner as that of the IOU venture. APPA has access to a 2,200 member organization of public power utilities nationwide and is a leader in energy technology commercialization. The goal of this effort, like the IOU venture, is an additional 100 MW in the 1990s.

Ft. St. Vrain PV Project. Public Service of Colorado has applied to the Colorado PUC to approve the installation of up to 14 MW of PV in conjunction with the retirement of the nuclear power plant. If the project is feasible and approved, the project may be completed by 1996.

Department of Defense (DOD) PV Project. DOD is the single largest energy consumer in the U.S. This project expects to deploy 100 MW of PV power by 1996. Likely projects include peaking, intermediate, and bulk power applications in the Southwest, and off-grid applications worldwide.

In addition, Solar 2000 hopes to consider projects with the U.S. Power Marketing Authorities (PMA). Besides wheeling power, with its large potential for PV line support and DSM applications, some PMAs engage in power generation which provides opportunities to demonstrate bulk power applications.

The Photovoltaics Design Assistance Center (DAC) continues lend technical assistance a number of projects such as the Niagara Mohawk Power Corporation PV demand-side management project in Albany, NY, as well as PV projects in a number of national forests in cooperation with the Department of Interior. The PV DAC is also providing assistance to the Virgin Islands Energy Office following the devastation of Hurricane Hugo.

Internationally, the primary focus will be on two projects: (a) Financing Energy Services for Small-Scale Energy Users (FINESSE) which is a DOE-sponsored effort in conjunction with other U.S. agencies and the World Bank, the Asian Development Bank, and the Netherlands to develop innovative approaches for providing power in rural and urban sectors throughout the developing world; and (b) Mexico Rural Electrification Project where DOE and US Agency for International Development are lending technical support to the national utility of Mexico in the development and implementation of a rural electrification program emphasizing renewable energy technology.

THE 1990S AND BEYOND

The DOE projects that 1,400 MW of U.S.-made PV systems will be installed worldwide by the year 2000. About 900 MW could be installed in the U.S. and another 500 MW installed overseas between 1991 and 2000 by U.S. companies (Figure 2). For comparison, approximately 100 MW of U.S. PV systems were installed worldwide during the 1980s (2).

Figure 2 - Projected U.S. PV Market Growth

The U.S. consumer, government, industrial, commercial, agricultural and grid-connected distributed applications are expected to account for about 15% each of the cumulative market in 2000. The bulk power market share is likely to be small at around 3%. The export market will be important for U.S. companies, and exports are expected to have a 36% market share. Electric utilities will be a principal user of PV, not only for grid-connected distributed applications, but more so for off-grid uses within their service territories.

A comparison between the market segmentation in 1990 and the projected market in year 2000 is shown in Figure 3. While exports continue their dominant market share, the actual share declines to 36% in 2000 from the 43% market share they held in 1990. The expansion in the industrial/commercial/agricultural and the utility grid-connected applications is clearly evident. The bulk power market share is small and represents primarily demonstration projects such as the Ft. St. Vrain project.

Figure 3 Comparison of 1990 and 2000 Market Segmentation

In order to achieve these projected cumulative sales, U.S. PV companies will need to expand PV production capacity to about

400 MW/year from today's capacity of about 20 MW/year. This corresponds to an expansion rate of about 35% a year, considerably faster than the current growth rate of 15% to 20% a year. The DOE believes that this faster growth rate can be achieved as a result of the concerted efforts under Solar 2000 as well as a greater acceptance and broader adoption of integrated resource planning methods; increasing environmental concerns leading to a move away from polluting technologies; a greater commitment by state and federal government agencies to use PV for cost-effective applications; and greater recognition by utilities that PV is cost-effective not only for remote off-grid applications, but for larger-scale applications as well.

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